

Complexes of Lower Valent Rhenium: $H_2[ReCl_5NO]$ and its Salts

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The preparation and the properties of a nitroschloride of rhenium, analogous to $RuNOCl_3$, was communicated earlier¹. The preparation of $H_2[ReCl_5NO]$ and some of its derivatives is now presented.

The nitroso-chloride of rhenium, $ReNOCl_3$, dissolves in concentrated hydrochloric acid with the formation of $H_2[ReCl_5NO]$, which cannot be isolated in the dry state owing to its extreme solubility and its tendency of ready elimination of hydrogen chloride. Salts of the acid with alkali metal ions or cations of organic bases have been prepared by the following more or less general procedure.

A concentrated solution of the nitroschloride in concentrated hydrochloric acid was refluxed for three hours with chlorides of alkali metals or hydrochlorides of organic bases in aqueous hydrochloric acid medium. The brown solution turned green. After evaporating to dryness on a water bath, the residue was extracted with a small volume of water, which on concentration yielded beautiful green crystals. These were usually purified by repeated crystallisation from slightly acidified aqueous solution or by removal of organic hydrochlorides with suitable organic solvents. The crystals were finally dried in vacuum to a constant weight.

By following this procedure salts of the general formula $M_n[ReCl_5NO]$ were prepared, where M stands for K^+ , Cs^+ , pyH^+ and enH_2^{++} . The potassium salt was found difficult to purify from adhering chloride impurities. The caesium salt was prepared easily in the pure state. A typical analysis of the caesium salt is as follows: Found, Re, 28.3; Cl, 26.8; Cs, 39.4; N, 2.2%; $Cs_n[ReCl_5NO]$ requires Re, 28.2; Cl, 26.9; Cs, 40.3; N, 2.1%.

The magnetic moment of the caesium salt was found to be 1.47 B.M. at 30°. This value, although lower than the theoretical, corresponds to one unpaired electron.

Both the caesium and potassium salts are extremely soluble in water and in aqueous ethanol, producing a beautiful green solution. Such solutions are ordinarily quite stable, but are easily decomposed by alkali and oxidising agents. An aqueous solution of the caesium salt shows absorption maxima at 210 $m\mu$, ($\log \epsilon=3.71$), 250 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon=3.27$), 305 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon=3.77$) and 640 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon=1.54$). The I.R. spectra of the caesium salt shows a sharp peak at 1710 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to the NO stretch.

On passing an aqueous solution of $Cs_n[ReCl_5NO]$ through a column of cation exchange

resin, Dowex 50 $\times$ H, the corresponding free acid $H_n[ReCl_nNO]$ was prepared. The aqueous solution on evaporation in a desiccator did not crystallise. The aqueous solution was green, and a potentiometric titration with sodium hydroxide indicated strong acidity. On the addition of an excess of alkali the colour of the solution turned red.

The salts of $H_n[ReCl_nNO]$ with organic bases like pyridine and ethylenediamine are also bright green and are beautifully crystalline. The ethylenediamine salt is difficult to purify from adhering ethylenediamine hydrochloride. But the pyridine salt was easily isolated in the pure state as needle-shaped crystals using chloroform as the wash liquid and by repeated crystallisation from hot ethanol. A typical analysis of the pyridinium salt is as follows: Found: Re, 32.8; C, 21.7; N, 7.3; Cl, 32.1%; $(pyH)_n[ReCl_nNO]$ requires Re, 33.6; C, 21.7; N, 7.6; Cl, 32.1%.

The pyridine and the ethylenediamine salts are highly soluble in water and moderately so in ethanol. The dry salts and their aqueous solutions are decomposed by alkali and also by oxidising agents but are otherwise quite stable.

The dry pyridinium salt on heating in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, was found to be stable up to about 190°. At this temperature loss of hydrogen chloride started and at 200°, the loss of one molecule of hydrogen chloride per molecule of the pyridinium salt was complete. The product obtained at this stage on analysis was found to contain Re, 36.4; N, 8.1; Cl, 28.5%; $pyH[ReCl_4pyNO]$ requires Re, 36.0; N, 8.2; Cl 27.5%.

This compound was heated further in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, and at 400° the loss of another molecule of hydrogen chloride per molecule of the monopyridinium salt occurred. The pale green amorphous residue was found to contain on analysis Re, 38.2; Cl, 23.1; calculated for $ReCl_3NOpy_2$; Re, 38.7; Cl, 22.2%.

The pyrolytic decomposition at these two stages may be represented by the following equations:

The isolation and characterisation of the derivatives of $[ReCl_nNOpy]^-$ by replacements of further chlorine atoms with ligands like ethylenediamine, oxalate ion etc. are in progress.

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